

**UNIVERSITY OF
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FLOW ASSURANCE ASSESSMENT FOR ARCTIC CONDITIONS

EG5908 Individual Project in Oil and Gas Engineering

By

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Abstract

The flow assurance of produced reservoir fluids from the wellhead to the processing facility is important to the success and cost-effective operation of production systems, especially under Arctic conditions. The technical challenges and huge developmental/operational cost of Arctic field operations necessitated a flow assurance assessment to investigate the Arctic specific flow assurance concerns such as gas hydrates, long tiebacks and low temperature in order to find a best-suit solution approach. In this study, PIPESIM simulator was used to model the thermal-hydraulic properties of the fluid along a 120 km Arctic subsea to onshore Ormen Lange pipeline. Three techniques for gas hydrate and low-temperature management were assessed, these include thermal insulation, direct electric heating (DEH) and thermodynamic inhibitors (methanol and mono-ethylene glycol (MEG)). The hydrate formation temperature (HFT) was determined from the model as 21°C and the thermal insulation thickness that gave a steady state operating temperature outside the HFT was 180mm. The estimated one-off investment cost for implementing thermal insulation was approximate \$126 million. Similarly, the electric power required to actively heat the entire pipeline and maintain an operating temperature above the HFT was determined to be 195 megawatts with an investment and operating cost of \$319 million and \$72 million per annum respectively. Again, the weight percent (wt%) and injection rate of methanol and MEG required to suppress the HFT below the operating temperature was obtained as 27.7 wt% methanol injected at 160.44 m³day⁻¹ and 45.3% MEG injected at 216.232 m³day⁻¹ respectively. The capital investment and operating cost were evaluated to be \$328 million and \$449 million for Methanol while \$878 million and \$292 million for MEG. Summarily, findings from the research showed that thermal insulation, Direct Electric Heating (DEH) and thermodynamic chemical injection alternatives assessed were all feasible alternatives, however with unique limitations and high points. But with respect to cost, reliability, and environmental friendliness, the DEH was considered the optimum alternative in this assessment for Arctic conditions flow assurance operation.

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Definitions
MEG	Mono-Ethylene Glycol
MeOH	Methanol
DEH	Direct Electric Heating
KHI	Kinetic Hydrate Inhibitors
AA	Anti-Agglomerates
HFT	Hydrate Formation Temperature
TAP	Trans- Alaska Pipeline
OHTC	Overall Heat Transfer Coefficient
SM ³	Standard Meter Cube
MM	Million
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure
OPEX	Operating Expenditure
WGR	Water Gas Ratio
GOR	Gas Oil Ratio
kWh	Kilowatt Hour
PVT	Pressure volume Temperature
PBC	Piggyback Cable
MW	Megawatt
PUF	Polyurethane Foam
PPF	Polypropylene Foam
PP	Polypropylene
CRA	Corrosion Resistant Alloys
MPa	Mega Pascal
kPa	Kilo-Pascal

CHAPTER ONE

1. Introduction

While the world oil and gas reserve continues to decline in the onshore and shallow waters (<305m below sea level), the global energy consumption remains on the rise and may hit almost a 30% increase by the year 2035 compared to the present consumption rate (Fig. 1.1) [1].

Figure 1.1: Global Energy Consumption by Fuel: Adapted from [1]

The oil and gas industry is challenged to employ best practice, best principle and best technologies to explore and recover all the technically recoverable hydrocarbon in deeper waters (>1200m below sea level) and Arctic regions to meet the ever growing energy demand to drive the industrialized world.

The Arctic, according to the United States Geological Survey (USGS) holds a total oil and natural gas resources approximating to 412 billion barrels of oil equivalent, of which 78 percent is natural gas and natural gas liquids [2]. In fact, a breakdown of the assessment showed that the Arctic holds nearly 22% of the earth's hydrocarbon resources, about 30% of the world's undiscovered conventional gas resources, about 13% of the world's undiscovered conventional oil resources, and 20% of the world's natural gas liquids (NGL) [3].

However, exploration and production operations in these regions are characterised by sub-zero temperature, harsh weather conditions, long distance tiebacks and uneven terrain

profile thereby necessitating the need for flow assurance. For instance, the high pressure and ice-chilled temperature in the Arctic presents a favourable condition for high heat transfer to the surrounding leading to the formation of plugs such as gas hydrates and paraffin wax which impede the free flow of produced fluids and may result in personnel safety and environmental hazards.

In addition, due to the sensitivity of the Arctic region, the subject of flow assurance is a critical part in the design and development of production and injection facilities. This is because the Arctic circle is susceptible to high developmental cost, as such, may become unprofitable when subjected to the outrageous cost associated with flow assurance failure and remediation [4]. In order to predict, identify, quantify, prevent and/or mitigate most of these free-flow hindrances shown in Fig.1.2, the thermal-hydraulic design and assessment of pipeline, subsea topographic survey, as well as other production and fluid transport systems are required to assure a safe, economical and unrestricted multiphase flow from the wellbore to the processing platform[5-8].

Figure 1.2: Flow Assurance Issues

1.1 Research Objectives

Main Aim: The main aim of this research was to model a subsea tieback under Arctic condition and analyse how low temperature, heat transfer, long step-out tiebacks and gas hydrates could be cost-effectively managed under Arctic operating conditions.

The objectives of this research are to:

- Identify with a clear description, conditions and challenges impacting on Arctic flow assurance with emphasis on long distance tiebacks, heat transfer, hydrates formation, scale formation, wax and asphaltene deposition through literature review.
- Determine via literature review how low-temperature issues can be prevented or mitigated effectively and economically in long distance tiebacks.
- Design a flow assurance model using PIPESIM with a case study of Ormen Lange gas field to demonstrate how the above-mentioned flow assurance challenges can be efficiently and cost effectively managed.
- Present a dissertation summarizing the knowledge gathered, the results obtained and a critical analysis of the findings from the research.

1.2 Case Study Field History and Production Performance

For the purpose of this study, Ormen Lange gas field was used as a case study. Ormen Lange is an offshore gas field discovered by Hydro in 1997, located about 100 km off the Norwegian coast in a pre-historic slide area (the Storegga slide), in water depth ranging from 850 to 1,100 meters.

Proven recoverable reserve from the field is estimated to be about 375 billion Sm³ gas and 22 million m³ condensate. The development option adopted was a subsea tieback of the subsea wells to an onshore processing terminal at Nyhamna via multiphase pipeline. In 2007, the implementation of the Ormen Lange Phase 1, comprising of two subsea templates connecting 8 well slots with well head pressure and temperature (9 to 25.5 MPa and 70°C) was undertaken.

The expected daily and annual export capacity from Ormen Lange at peak production are 70 million Sm³ and 21 billion Sm³ respectively based on the current daily production of approximately 10 million Sm³ per well.

The choice of Ormen Lange for this study is because of its Arctic characteristics which make it prone to most flow assurance issues triggered by:

- Sub-zero ambient temperature at seabed (- 2°C)
- Long distance tieback of about 120km to onshore processing facilities
- Rough and uneven terrain of seafloor
- Harsh weather conditions.

1.3 Research Scope and Limitations

The boundaries of this research enveloped a concise description of the major flow assurance issues associated with Arctic field operations, identified their causes, and methods of prevention or mitigation. The design and analysis were performed with Schlumberger's PIPESIM steady state multiphase simulator.

The limitation of this research was the inability to analyse efficiently transient conditions such as start-up, shutdown, slugging, and pigging operations which required a dynamic simulator such as OLGA.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Description of Natural Gas Hydrate

Natural gas hydrates are best described as a solid ice-like crystalline structure (clathrate) formed from a hydrogen bonding of hydrocarbon molecule, and a water molecule when the hydrocarbon molecule has been completely caged by the water molecule. The hydrocarbon molecule also referred to as the guest molecule may include methane, ethane, propane, butane, isobutane, carbon dioxide and hydrogen sulfide.

However, methane is the most abundantly occurring guest molecule in natural gas hydrates [6]. Three commonly known hydrate crystal structures are structure I (sI), structure II (sII) and structure H (sH), but only structures I and II are identified in oil and gas operation with well-defined properties. Hydrate structures I and II were discovered in the 1940s and 1950s respectively while the structure H was identified in 1987 [5, 6].

The structure II is normally formed by heavier molecules unlike structure I, but this is not always the case as the structure of hydrate crystal formed are influenced by the size of the guest molecule, the prevailing temperature and pressure of the system [9].

Figure 2.1: Natural gas hydrate structures: Adapted from [10]

The structures I, II and H are formed when the basic building block consisting of 12 pentagonal faces (5¹²) formed by water molecule combines with its like either in addition to 2 hexagonal faces 5¹²6² (structure I), 4 hexagonal faces 5¹²6⁴ (structure II), and a

combination two other structures made of 3 squares, 6 pentagon, 3 hexagonal faces $4^35^66^3$ combined with 12 pentagon and 8 hexagonal faces $5^{12}6^8$ (structure H) as shown in Fig.2.1.

Also, accepted generally is the fact that hydrate nuclei forms at the gas-water interface, but how the gas molecules migrate into the water cavities at a given pressure and temperature is a phenomenon not well understood [10, 11]. However, the formation of gas hydrates is most favoured when the gas is at the hydrate temperature, pressure, and below its water dew point. And once the hydrate crystal nucleation starts, the growth is greatly affected by the diffusive flux of gas and water molecules, turbulence, nucleation sites for crystal formation/agglomeration and the salinity of the system [6, 11].

Although hydrate shares similar physical properties as ice, gas hydrates can form at a temperature well above the ice formation in a pressurized system [10]. Generally, the hydrate temperature and pressure of a particular gas depend on its composition, nevertheless, because temperature varies directly with pressure, increasing the pressure of the gas increases the chances of hydrate formation [9]. This explains why the risk of hydrate plugs is higher for gas handling systems at transient conditions such as start-up, shut-in and downstream of choke as the temperature drops due to the Joule-Thompson cooling effect [5, 6].

In other words, gas hydrate presents a high operational risk of blockages for offshore and Arctic field development. And because of the technical hitches and cost impact of mitigating gas hydrate related flow assurance issues, over the past years efforts in research has been focused on finding ways to predict, prevent and mitigate challenges of hydrate formation in conventional hydrocarbon handling systems particularly for regions attributed with very low ambient temperature such as offshore, deepwater and Arctic region [12].

2.2 Prediction and Detection of Natural Gas Hydrate Formation

The ability to detect the onset of hydrate formation is instrumental in eliminating the big challenge of blockage or rupture of the pipeline as a result of hydrate formation. Different approach and technology are currently in place within the oil and gas industry to detect hydrate formation in subsea pipeline. These hydrate formation detective technology and technique include pigging return, observation of the changes in the pressure and flow rate

at the separator using differential pressure sensors, acoustic sensing gadgets or gamma ray densitometers with temperature sensing.

2.2.1 K-Factor Method:

Carson and Katz [13] discovered this method of hydrate prediction using the vapour and solid (hydrate) equilibrium constant of hydrocarbon composition. The K-factor technique to predict hydrate temperature and pressure is an iterative one, and the equation governing the conditions of hydrate formation is given in equation 2.1 below.

$$x_i = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{y_i}{K_i} \right) = 1.0 \quad (2.1)$$

Where x_i and y_i are the mole fraction of component i in solid and vapour respectively on a water-free basis, K_i is the vapour-solid equilibrium.

The temperature and pressure at which the condition of equation 2.1 is met, is considered as the hydrate equilibrium stability temperature.

2.2.2 Pigging Returns:

Pipeline inspection gauges (PIG) are forced through the pipeline via a pressure source to inspect pipeline internals, clean up debris and prevent the blocking of the flow by wax, hydrates and other particles that form in the pipeline. The pigging return method of predicting hydrate is anchored on the practical experience that hydrate particles are often found in pig traps prior to the time the hydrate will metamorphose to form blockages in the pipeline. Therefore, an early observation of these warning (hydrate particles) could help implement corrective measure such as increasing the chemical injection rate and volume or increase the heating rate. Based on the above fact, it is a good practice to investigate properly the pigging return for evidence of hydrate particle formation.

2.2.3 Monitoring Pressure drop (ΔP)

This approach for hydrate prediction is based on the general principle of pressure drop across an orifice or a restriction. Because the flow pressure is influenced by the pipe diameter, the presence of hydrates which restrict flow in the pipeline will increase the pressure drop and reduce the flow rate of the fluid. Although the change in flow rate can be observed, that of pressure drop is better monitored because the pressure drop in

pipeline is equal to the square root of the turbulent flow rate which makes it bigger to be observed

2.2.4 Changes in flow rate and composition at receiving terminal

The change in flowrate method of prediction is based on the knowledge that the host molecule for hydrate formation is water, and a major guest molecule is methane. Therefore, a significant reduction in the amount of water produced in the separator or changes in the composition of the natural gas produced (possible reduction in the mole of methane) could be an indication of hydrate formation in the pipeline as such should be monitored closely

2.2.5 Acoustic Sensors/detectors along subsea pipeline

The acoustic reflectometry method for hydrate detection uses the same principles as sand monitoring instruments. Pulse of sound are injected into the pipeline, and the acoustic sensor records the reflection produced as the signal travels along the pipeline. As such locations in the flowline with partial or total blockages will produce high reflection and the interpretation and analysis of the reflection helps to identify locations of hydrate formation. Although this technique is used onshore for hydrate sensing, it has no subsea application yet [14].

2.2.6 Gamma Ray Densitometers with temperature sensing.

Although the possibility of transmitting gamma ray to the sensor is dependent on the thickness of the pipe, the gamma ray densitometers technique functions with emitter and sensor positioned opposite to each other on the external wall of the pipe. It combines the gamma ray and a temperature sensing device because the gamma ray densitometer may not distinguish exactly between the density of water and hydrate. But because hydrate is associated with low temperature which is attributed to the Joule-Thomson effect and possibly high density whereas water maintains same heat as the natural gas, the conclusion in this method of hydrate prediction is that a low temperature, high-density region could be an indication of hydrate formation in the pipeline whereas a high temperature and high density is likely a water slug [15].

2.3 Gas Hydrate Prevention and Remediation Techniques

The high cost of intervention, lost in production revenue and technical bottlenecks associated with gas hydrate blockages particularly in arctic environment and offshore subsea systems increases the need for a proper and adequate hydrate management strategy to ensure hydrate crystal does not agglomerate and form blockages in the pipeline system during start-up, normal production operations or following a shut-in [4].

The most efficient way to prevent hydrate plugs remains to get rid of water (both produced and condensed) in the hydrocarbon system, but because this may not be technically and economically best option, to achieve success in hydrate prevention for any of the above scenarios will require either an approach that will keep the operating conditions outside the hydrate temperature and pressure (insulation or active heating), thermodynamically suppress the hydrate temperature by chemical injection (MeOH and MEG), use low dosage inhibitors (KHI or AA), or apply the newly patented technology of cold flow to prevent or reduce the rate of hydrate crystal agglomeration.

2.3.1 Thermal Methods of Hydrate Prevention

The thermal prevention strategy makes use of heat conservation (passive method) or introduction (active method) to the system in order to maintain the fluid temperature well above the hydrate formation envelope. The objective of the thermal prevention method can be achieved in any of the following ways: thermal insulation, electrical heating, hot-oil circulation and bundles.

However, the rate of heat absorption and retention of liquids compared to gas must be put into consideration in the selection of a thermal prevention approach for Arctic pipeline operations. Because of its high density and thermal mass, liquids have a better heat retention time as such pipelines carrying liquids, particularly oil are suitable for hydrate mitigation strategy using thermal insulation [5]. Unlike the oil, gas density and thermal mass (density times heat capacity) are much smaller, as such thermal insulation will not be very effective for gas handling systems and pipelines due to the low heat retention of gases.

2.3.1.1 Thermal Insulation

The heat energy in the pipeline fluid can be conserved by maintaining a very low overall heat transfer to the ambient surrounding through dry or wet thermal insulation method [16]. However, achieving this low overall heat transfer coefficient (OHTC) is both a function of the thermophysical and mechanical properties of the pipeline materials and the type, thickness, thermal conductivity and OHTC of the insulation material used as they are important properties of the thermal insulator that largely influence the OHTC [17].

Therefore, prior to the design of any approach of thermal insulation, some flow assurance analysis are required such as:

- Flash analysis of reservoir fluid composition to find out the hydrate formation temperature at the expected operating pressure and flowrate.
- Thermal Hydraulics analysis of the pipeline to ascertain the OHTC needed at every location based on the pipeline thermal conductivity in relation to the ambient temperature at that location.
- Transient heat transfer analysis in some positions along the pipeline to generate a cooldown profile and the corresponding times.

The above analysis are key because without the knowledge of the hydrate temperature, the thermal requirement of the pipeline nor the maximum cool-down time, there is a likelihood of over-designing which is a wasted cost or at worst case an under-design which renders the solution ineffective.

2.3.1.2 Pipe-In-Pipe Thermal Insulation

Experience and research have shown that the pipe-in-pipe method of thermal insulation has some merits over the conventional wet insulation approach particularly the high chance of lower OHTC because of the very low thermal conductivity of the insulation materials such as polyurethane foam, fiberglass, aerogel, microporous silica and mineral wool used as shown in Fig 2.2.

This low OHTC favours high internal fluid temperature and flow conditions. Nevertheless, PIP has a high risk of corrosion in the event of water ingress and it is limited to a certain pipe size which in turn limits the water depth it could be installed.

Similarly, although PIP thermal insulation is practiced in some subsea tiebacks depending on distance and capabilities of the topside platform, it lacks strong feasibility when considering the fluid (gas and condensate) cool-down time during shutdown.

Another setback of the PIP is the possibility of manually pulling the insulation material into the pipeline for a pipe-in-pipe insulation using the reel or tow bottom pipeline installation method and the cost implication of thermally insulating very long distance tiebacks in offshore and Arctic environments such as the 800-miles Trans Alaska Pipeline (TAP) and the over 110km tieback of Snohvit and Ormen Lange fields off the Norwegian coast [18, 19].

2.3.1.3 Burial in Soil

The technique of using the soil as a thermal insulation is a proven one, but several attempts made to bury pipeline in deep-waters and then use the soil as thermal insulation materials is not yet a success because of the excess water that will evolve from the covering soil thereby making the convective heat transfer significant.

2.3.1.4 Thermotite ®ULTRA™

According to Shiwei et al [20], the novel thermal wet insulation system based on styrene alloys has many unique advantages over the insulation materials (e.g. PUF, PPF, epoxy forms, syntactic, solids,) which includes limitless water depth, lower thickness, advanced cool-down performance and low-temperature flexibility.

The Thermotite ®ULTRA™ pipeline insulation system is made up of 3-layer corrosion inhibition coating comprising primarily a fusion bonded epoxy (FBE), an adhesive layer (ULTRABond) and lastly a styrenic based outer-coat (ULTRASolid). In addition to the very low OHTC of the Thermotite ULTRA, its higher density is strategic in optimising hydrodynamic response in risers as well as ensuring the stability of pipeline at the seafloor. The thermotite ULTRA system have been used in Goliat off northern Norway and the Balboa field in the Gulf of Mexico

2.3.1.5 Active Thermal Prevention Methods

Several approaches exists and have been practiced in actively introducing heat to pipeline amongst others are electric heating, bundles and hot oil circulation. In the midst of all, electrical heating of pipelines to maintain fluid temperature outside the wax deposition

and hydrate formation zone has gained attractive attention in flow assurance operations following the advent of deep-water and Arctic operation where very long distance tiebacks are required and mostly ice-chilled ambient temperature such as the case of Ormen Lange.

It involves the introduction of heat to the pipeline and the fluid therein via a direct or indirect heat transfer mechanism depending on whether the current is flowing directly to the pipeline to be heated or through another element on the pipe surface which then heats the pipeline by thermal conduction [21, 22] as shown in Fig.2.3.

The electric method of heating pipeline functions effectively to prevent blockages of gas hydrates at all operating conditions as well as used for intervention and remediation when plugs have already formed. The technique was implemented for hydrate plug remediation in Nakika's North production system, an onshore Arctic field designed by Shell and operated by British Petroleum [23].

Figure 2.3: Open loop direct electric heating overview: Adapted from [24]

2.3.2 Chemical Inhibitions of Natural Gas Hydrate

Two main categories of hydrate inhibition chemicals are well known and used in the industry for gas hydrate blockage prevention and they are thermodynamic inhibitors (methanol (MeOH), monoethylene glycol (MEG)) and Low-dosage hydrate inhibitors (LDHIs) such as kinetic inhibitors (KI) and anti-agglomerate (AA).

2.3.2.1 Thermodynamic Hydrate Inhibitors (THI)

The thermodynamic inhibitors functions in a way such that it thermodynamically causes the fluid hydrate formation pressure to increase while the temperature reduces without affecting the nucleation of the hydrate crystals nor the growth rate of the crystal to form blockages [10]. The impact of a continuous 10% MeOH increase in reducing the hydrate formation zone thereby increasing the hydrate free zone is illustrated from the model Multiflash plot in Fig. 2.4 below.

Figure 2.4: Effect of methanol injection on hydrate formation temperature

Also, because MeOH and MEG have different molecular masses, their mode of injection is not the same. Methanol with lesser molecular mass (32g) is easily vaporised into the gas phase, mixes with the gas and flows together thereby reducing the water concentration and hydrate formation temperature of the gas but very expensive and technically not simple to regenerate [25].

The attraction to methanol in oil system is mostly because of its less viscosity which reduces the drop in pressure along the pipeline unlike MEG. On the other hand, because of methanol's high flammability, toxicity and poisonousness to catalysts in downstream systems, MEG which is non-volatile, nonpoisonous and easily recoverable due to its high molecular mass (62g) is preferable in some parts of the world such as the Middle East, Pacific Rim and the North Sea particularly for gas systems [10].

Regardless the fact that hydrate inhibition normally takes place at the free water phase, a non-negligible amount of methanol goes to the vapour and hydrocarbon liquid phase. As such, to obtain the total inhibitor injection rate, a product of the inhibitor concentration in each phase and the phase flow rate is required [26]. The concentration of the inhibitor required in the free water phase can be ascertained using the Hammerschmidt or the Nielson and Bucklin (1983) equation [27].

$$X_i = \frac{M_i \Delta T_h}{K_i + M_i \Delta T_h} \times 100 \quad (2.2)$$

Where X_i is weight percentage of inhibitor in water phase, ΔT_h is depression of hydrate formation temperature, and M_i is the molecular weight of inhibitor and K_i is a constant (MEG = 2220, MeOH = 1297).

$$X_i = \frac{n_i M_i}{18.015 + n_i (M_i - 18.015)} \quad (2.3)$$

Where n_i is given as:

$$n_i = 1 - \exp\left(\frac{-\Delta T_h}{72}\right) \quad (2.4)$$

Also, brines such as NaCl affects the conditions of hydrate formation by shifting the temperature (temperature reduction) as the concentration of salt increases. But the practice of this method of hydrate inhibition lost relevance for two reasons (1) the solubility of brines in water is limited based on the systems' temperature and beyond this limit, hydrate will start to form rapidly; (2) the damaging effect of salt such as scale deposition and corrosion of process facility [5].

2.3.2.2 Low Dosage Hydrate Inhibitors (LDHI)

Thermodynamic inhibitors have been effective for over 75 years [28]. However, its ever increasing OPEX, especially at high water content, gave the impetus for a low dosage hydrate inhibiting chemical that could still achieve similar or even more than the traditional thermodynamic hydrate inhibitors [29, 30]. These LDHI chemicals are of two categories: kinetic inhibitors and anti-agglomerates.

But regrettably, several studies on KHI established that the functionality of the kinetic inhibitors is limited to significantly delaying the hydrate crystal nucleation and growth process for a longer period normally more than the free water residence time in the flow lines by bonding to the hydrate surface but does not absolutely prevent the nucleation process [10, 29].

This implies that the KHI is time dependent and once this time is elapsed, hydrate blockage will rapidly form in the pipeline. The maximum time KHI can effectively prevent hydrate crystal growth is called the 'hold-time' ranging from 24 to 48 hours, which means that the fluid residence time in the pipeline must be lower than this time to avoid hydrate issues [5]. Also, another ranking factor for KHI is the amount of sub-cooling they are capable of giving below the equilibrium temperature at a defined pressure. This sub-cooling temperature for KHI is within the range of 15 - 23°F (-9 to -5°C) whereas for deep-waters and the Arctic the sub-cooling is normally greater than 25°F (-3.9°C), this fact further limits the applicability of the KHI for the Arctic region [29].

2.3.2.3 The Anti-Agglomerates (AA)

The anti-agglomerates (AAs), basically long molecules (polymers and surfactants) functions differently from the kinetic inhibitors. AAs does not delay the hydrate crystal nucleation process but hinders the development and metamorphosing of large hydrate crystal into a hydrate blockage. This is achieved by suspending the water phase which is converted to hydrate crystals in the hydrocarbon as a small transportable slurry and moves together with the hydrocarbon thereby preventing hydrate blockage up-to about 50% concentration in the water phase [10].

The AAs has no limitation of sub-cooling in practice as it effectively sub-cools up-to 40°F (4.5°C). Nevertheless, for gas and condensate system, the effectiveness of the AAs is mainly a function of the amount of condensate in the system, that is to say, the volume of the continuous oil phase available determines its performance [25].

Table 2.1: Summary of Applications, Merits and Shortfalls of chemical hydrate inhibitors [30, 31].

Thermodynamic Inhibitors	Kinetic Inhibitors	Anti-Agglomerates
Applications		
i. Multiphase flow ii. Gas, Condensate and Crude oil	i. Multiphase flow ii. Gas, condensate and crude oil	i. Multiphase flow ii. Condensate and crude oil.
Merits/Benefits		
i. Robust and effective in performance ii. Well understood iii. Predictable with a model iv. Proven track-record	i. Reduced CAPEX & OPEX ii. Reduced volume (<1wt %) iii. None toxic and Environmentally friendly iv. Tested in gas systems	i. Reduced CAPEX & OPEX ii. Reduced volume (< 1wt %) iii. Non-toxic and Environmentally friendly iv. Reasonable range sub-cool
Demerits/Shortfalls		
i. High CAPEX & OPEX required ii. High Volume required (10 – 60 wt %) iii. Hazardous, Toxic and environmentally harmful iv. Volatile-losses to vapour (MeOH) v. ‘Salting out’	i. Limited Subcooling (<10°C) ii. Time dependent functionality iii. Not effective at shutdowns iv. System specific-testing v. Not generally compatibility vi. Precipitation at high temperature vii. Not very effective in oil systems viii. No predictive model yet.	i. Time dependent functionality ii. Not effective at shutdowns iii. Only used for low watercuts iv. System specific-testing v. Not generally compatible vi. Not in wide range of application vii. No predictive model

2.3.3 Cold Stabilized Flow Technology

The cold flow technology for hydrate blockage prevention differs from the thermal and thermodynamic approach in that it allows the formation of hydrates but in a controlled system. The formed hydrate crystals are transported together with the bulk wellstream as slurry as such does not plug the flowline.

Recently, research efforts have been focused on the cold flow technology because of the merits of low CAPEX and OPEX it promises for long distance tieback hydrate prevention which is the trending challenge in deep-waters and Arctic reservoir fluid transportation.

SINTEF-BP Technique: SINTEF and British Petroleum (BP) developed a dry gas hydrate recycling process for converting free water into hydrate which flows as slurry [32, 33]. This approach is based on the argument that recycling fluid bearing some dry gas hydrates will create nucleation sites for more hydrates crystal to form in the presence of water and flow as a slurry in the oil.

HYDRAFLOW Technique: The HYDRAFLOW concept unlike the dry hydrate technology functions basically by allowing the gas hydrate to form regardless of the water content, but apply low dose anti-agglomerates to prevent the agglomeration of the solid hydrate crystals into larger hydrates and result to blockage. The summary of the concept is to reduce or eliminate the gas phase possibly by converting the gas to hydrates via a reaction with water (produced or injected) [32].

2.3.3.1 Merits of Cold flow Technology

- i. It eliminates the high cost of pipeline insulation, active heating and thermodynamic chemical inhibitors (MeOH and MEG) for long tiebacks as well as reduce the dose of AA required if necessary.
- ii. It reduces the risk of severe slugging as the density difference of phases (gas, oil and water) is reduced when the gas are all converted to hydrate slurry.
- iii. It eliminates the need for a hydrate reactor (equipment that reacts to produce hydrate in oil or water slurry) for gas transportation system in subsea.
- iv. Finally, it also reduces the issue of wax deposition by maintaining fluid temperature reasonably high due to the exothermic reaction of hydrate formation and /or by providing a nucleation site for wax in the fast moving hydrate slurry rather than pipeline wall.

2.3.3.2 Limitations of Cold Flow Technology

- i. The SINTEX experiment was performed for seabed temperature of 4°C, not for arctic conditions with sub-zero temperature almost all year round in some regions.
- ii. Also HYDRAFLOW experiment shows that this technology can only be feasible for very low GOR system because for high GOR such as a gas well which is the case of this study, the rate of hydrate formation will result to pipeline blockage even in the presence of AA at 4°C how much more sub-zero temperature range of the Arctic.

2.3.4 Depressurisation (Blowdown)

The depressurisation technique is based on the fact that reducing the pressure of the hydrate surface below the hydrate dissociation pressure, and the temperature will fall drastically below the ambient temperature, as such with time, the hydrate states melting from the pipe walls due to heat influx from the surrounding.

The system Depressurisation technique is able to remediate hydrate blockage in flowlines or set the flowline outside hydrate crystal formation when the shut-in period is longer than the cool-down period. And the performance is apparently faster for uninsulated pipeline (e.g. gas pipeline) compared to insulated or buried pipes because greater and faster heat influx penetrates the pipeline from the surrounding. From a safety perspective, depressurisation is recommended to be via both ends of the pipeline. This is because depressurizing from one end increases the risk of eruption of high-speed hydrate projectile due to the large pressure differential created across the plug [31]. The major setbacks of the blowdown technique is the time consumed in the process which is a lost in production time, the challenge encountered in depressurizing pipeline with uneven terrain (hilly and low spots) and the possibility that the host facility may not handle all the fluid leaving the pipeline.

2.3.5 Dehydration (Water Removal)

Natural gas hydrate equilibrium or stability will be impossible in the absence of the host molecule water. Particularly for gas production and transportation, dehydration is a proven approach to prevent the formation of gas hydrate in flowline.

Produced or condensed water in the flowlines can be removed either by subsea separators or installing pipeline drips near and/or strategically along the flowlines [6]. Similarly lowering the natural gas dew point temperature at which water vapour will condense using a liquid solvent (glycol), solid desiccants (crystalline structure) or refrigeration (cooling the gas) will prevent hydrate formation. The solvent and solid desiccants technique make use of mass transfer of the water molecule into the solvent or the solid desiccants whereas the refrigeration involves condensing the water molecule to liquid by cooling followed by a chemical injection.

2.3.6 Mechanical Method (Coiled Tubing)

The use of pipeline pigging process is not recommended for hydrate removal because of the tendency to complicate issue due to pig stuck. However, coiled tubing is a proven alternative for hydrate plug removal depending on the position of the hydrate blockage.[31]

2.4 Safety in Hydrate Removal Process

Avoiding hydrate blockage remains the best practice for oil and gas flow operations especially in the Arctic. However if hydrates has already clogged the pipeline, a safe removal process is essential as improper removal approach (Depressurisation or heating) could result to hydrate plug removal hazard caused either by eruption of hydrate projectile or excess pressure increase upon a rapid heat application on the pipeline both of which leads to severe damage to equipment, injury to operator or pollution of the environment. A Rule of thumb for proper hydrate plug removal suggests [14, 34]:

- Perform hydrate removal operation with the assumption that the plugs are multiple and there is a chance of pressure confined between the plugs.
- Be conscious of the fact that hydrate and /or ice plug removal could cause rupture of pipeline and other process facilities.
- When Depressurisation is the approach employed for plug removal, the blow-down should be done from both ends of the pipeline if possible.
- Application of heat for hydrate plug removal should be performed with an assurance of no trapped pressure in all ends of the pipeline.

2.5 Hydrodynamics: Slugging

Intermittent or slug flow pattern, although common to pipeline systems along uneven terrain and abnormal flowrate are caused either by pigging operation or ramp-up operations. If not managed properly (particularly the subsea riser to platform separator unit) may develop to severe slugging which increases the risk of topside process systems upset and probably shuts down the entire production system [35].

Severe Slugging is an extreme and special form of terrain induced (hydrodynamic) slugging and the possibility of it to occur is higher for a multiphase flow system towards the late field life, when liquid and gas flow pressure is declined such that the liquid is unable to lift itself up through the riser or hilly terrains along the pipeline routes.

The occurrence of severe slugging is a four-stage process of slug generation, slug formation, gas penetration and finally gas blowdown. Three basic conditions are required for severe riser slugging to occur which includes [36, 37]:

- The presence of a downward pipeline inclination just before the riser inlet position
- Fluid flowing in stratified or segregated flow regime as it approaches the riser
- Pots' number (slug number or PI-SS) less than or equal to unity.

$$\pi_{ss} = \frac{W_g}{W_l} \frac{ZRT}{M_g g L (1 - H_l)} \leq 1 \quad (2.2)$$

Where π_{ss} is the Pot's number, W_g , W_l are the gas and liquid mas flowrate, Z is the gas compressibility, R is the gas constant, T is the pipeline temperature, M_g is the gas molecular mass, L is pipeline length, g is acceleration gravity and H_l is the liquid hold-up.

2.6 Wax Deposition

Paraffin-wax are long chain/heavy molecular weight hydrocarbon (C17- C60) that are naturally contained in crude oil but solidifies due to a reduction in crude temperature or decrease in pressure below the bubble point. Wax crystals precipitate first at the wax appearance temperature (WAT) or cloud point. If the temperature decreases further below the WAT the fluid cools and begins to form gel [38]. At a certain low temperature, the waxy crude will stop to flow when poured and this temperature at which the crude can no

longer flow is called the pour point. Waxy crude are very viscous, hence result in more pressure losses due to friction, reduce pipe diameter and will require high start-up pumping pressure. Ultimately wax deposition could lead to total pipeline blockage and subsequent increase in OPEX for reheating the system. The prevention or inhibition of wax is mostly by thermal method (insulation or heating), chemical injection, or mechanical method (pigging, scraping and brushing).

2.7 Asphaltenes Precipitation

Asphaltenes are a high molecular weight component of crude oil, insoluble in n-pentane and n-heptane but soluble in toluene and benzene. This preferential solubility of asphaltenes explains why it will precipitate faster in a system containing excess n-pentane and n-heptane than toluene [5].

Changes in the thermodynamic properties (eg. drop in pressure below the bubble point and temperature), fluid composition, turbulent flow (high shear), comingling incompatible crude or gas, and the presence of acids induces asphaltenes fluctuation and deposition in any location (reservoir, well tubing or flowlines) [39, 40].

Unlike wax, when asphaltenes solidify, it is nearly impossible to melt it back to liquid by means of heating, therefore, must be prevented or inhibited by a continuous injection of chemicals that suppress the flocculation pressure of the aliphatic fraction of the crude oil or via a mechanical approach such as pipeline pigging.

2.8 Scale Formation

Scale precipitation occurs once the brine is supersaturated (solubility is exceeded) as a result of high concentration or changes in temperatures.

Most occurring scales in the oil and gas industry are calcium carbonate (CaCO_3) referred as calcite which is induced by CO_2 injection during enhanced oil recovery, barium sulfate (BaSO_4) commonly called barite, calcium sulfate (CaSO_4) and Strontium sulfate (SrSO_4) which are triggered and /or favoured by the injection of incompatible sea water rich in SO_4 into the reservoir during water flooding or water injection [41].

Major factors that influence the rate of scale precipitation and deposition in the hydrocarbon handling systems include the rate of temperature and pressure change,

changes in solutions pH, the concentration of basic particulates or impurities and level of agitation as the scale forms[42, 43].

Scales are prevented once any of the above causes of its deposition is eliminated, but in the event that they form, the chemical method could be used to dissolve scales or mechanical method such as pigging (brushing and scraping) depending on the hardness of blockage formed.

2.9 Corrosion Reactions

Corrosion is described as the process of metal material deterioration/erosion, mainly because of its reaction with the environment or handling media. The complex phenomenon corrosion and its management in gas, oil and water multiphase system is a vital flow assurance concern and calls for a good understanding of the produced fluid chemistry, pipeline material metallurgy and the multiphase flow hydraulics.

With the presence of water in oil and gas produced from the reservoir, depending on the concentration of acid gases such as CO₂, H₂S, the thermodynamics of fluid in the pipeline (temperature and pressure), fluid pH and the flow conditions (rate and regime), the internal wall of the pipeline is at risk of corrosion of different forms such as galvanic, pitting, cavitation, hydrogen attacks and many others [5]. Regardless of the form, the consequences of corrosion such as pipeline rupture and/or hydrocarbon handling system failure resulting in leaks and spillage poses a high threat to the environment particularly for subsea systems and the Arctic conditions which in-turn impacts on the OPEX of the investment. Industry practice for corrosion control includes the use of corrosion resistant alloys (CRA) in the place of carbon steel, corrosion inhibiting chemicals, plastic surface coating or cathodic protection [5, 44].

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

Several techniques are used in the industry today for flow assurance realisation, however, some of the alternative techniques offer a noticeable advantage (technical or economical) over others. For this reason, thermal insulation, thermodynamic inhibitors (Methanol and Ethylene glycol) and direct electric heating techniques were assessed using PIPESIM simulator to determine a best-case scenario for Arctic field development with regards to flow assurance in this study. Figure 3.1 shows the flowchart of the methodology for the flow assurance assessment in the Arctic condition.

Figure 3.1: Flowchart showing Flow Assurance Assessment Process

3.2 Data Collection and Field History

The data required for the model include: produced fluid composition, individual well/field peak production rate, wellhead pressure/temperature and water production rate. This data were collected from the studies of Arild et al [19], Burns et al [45], Anders et al [46] and Lunde et al [47] carried-out on the Ormen Lange gas field and tabulated in Table 3.1 to Table 3.6 below.

Table 3.1: Boundary Conditions

Reservoir Pressure	29 MPa
Reservoir Temperature	86 - 93 °C
Well Head Pressure (Inlet Pressure at subsea manifold)	9 – 25.5 MPa
Well Head Temperature (Inlet Pressure at subsea manifold)	70 °C
Peak Liquid Flow rate	70 MMsm ³ .d ⁻¹
Maximum turndown	20 MMsm ³ .d ⁻¹
Minimum arrival Pressure at 1 st stage separator	9 MPa

Table 3.2: Pure Hydrocarbon Components

Components	Mole %
Nitrogen (N ₂)	0.36
Carbon dioxide (CO ₂)	0.30
Methane (C1)	93.21
Ethane (C2)	3.55
Propane (C3)	1.32
Isobutane (IC4)	0.25
Butane (NC4)	0.36
Isopentane (IC5)	0.15
Pentane (NC5)	0.15
Hexane (NC6)	0.20
Heptane (C7)	0.15
Total	100 %

Table 3.3: Aqueous Component

Component	Year 2008-2021	Year 2022-2028	Year 2030-2034
Water production (Sm ³ /sd)	240	335	170
WGR (m ³ /mmsm ³)	(WGR 3.00 m ³ /mmsm ³)	(WGR 4.20 m ³ /mmsm ³)	(WGR 2.13 m ³ /mmsm ³)

Table 3.4: Other Base Data

Parameters	Value
Liquid flow rates for 8 of wells (mmSm ³ /d)	20,40,60,70 mmSm ³ d ⁻¹
Maximum formation water production	50 Sm ³ d ⁻¹
Seabed Ambient temperature	-2 °C
Sand grain size	Nil

Table 3.5: Flowline Data

Onshore and water depth	Ambient temperature	Flowline Length and inclination
Ambient temperature at onshore	16 °C	1km
Ambient temperature at 200m	12 °C	2 km (25° inclination)
	12 °C	100 km (10° undulations)
Ambient temperature at 600m	4 °C	103 km (30° inclination)
Ambient temperature at 900m (seabed)	-2 °C	120 km (30° inclination)
Wall thickness		35.5 mm (0.0355m)
Roughness		0.0000254 m
Flowlines sizes		25", 30", 36", 40" (0.635m, 0.762m, 0.915m, 1.016m)

Table 3.6: Pipeline and Insulation Thermal Properties

Parameters	Value
Pipe thermal conductivity	35 W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
Insulation thermal conductivity	0.21 W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
Insulation thickness	To be determined
Ambient fluid (water) velocity at 200m water depth	1.20 ms ⁻¹
Ambient fluid (water) velocity at 600 m water depth	0.95 ms ⁻¹
Ambient fluid (water) velocity at 900 m water depth	0.65 ms ⁻¹
Ambient fluid (Air) velocity	1.3 ms ⁻¹
Burial depth	Blank (elevated above ground)
Ground conductivity	2.595 W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹

Table 3.7 Physical Properties of Pure MEG and Methanol (MeOH)

S/N	Parameters	MEG	MeOH
1	Empirical Formula	C ₂ H ₆ O ₂	CH ₃ OH
2	Molecular Weight	62 gmol ⁻¹	32 g ⁻¹ mol
3	Boiling Point @ 100 kPa	197 °C	64.7°C
4	Vapour pressure at 20 °C	7.999 Pa	13.0 kPa
5	Density at 20 °C	1115 kgm ⁻³	791 kgm ⁻³
7	Freezing point	-13.4 °C	-98°C
8	Viscosity at 25 °C	16.9 cp	0.544 cp

3.3 Model Design Procedure in PIPESIM

The following stepwise methodology will serve as the base procedure for designing and analysing the 120 km Ormen Lange subsea tieback model using PIPESIM 2010.1.

- Step 1:** Launch PIPESIM and Select New Single Branch Model. (This is because the wells are commingled at the subsea manifold and transported with the same tieback system to the processing facility onshore).
- Step 2:** In the Units menu under Setup tab, set the units as SI.
- Step 3:** From the Setup tab, flow correlations menu, select Beggs & Brill Revised for both vertical and horizontal Flow correlations.
- Step 4:** From the Compositional template properties, set PVT Package as Multiflash equation of state (Peng-Robinson).
- Step 5:** Set Fluid compositional properties using base data from Tables 3.2 and 3.3.
- Step 6:** Select and connect physical model objects (well head, flow lines, and reports) and define input parameters using base data from Tables 3.1, 3.4 and 3.5.
- Step 7:** Run Model and Analyse results.
- Step 8:** From the Compositional template plot the Multiflash phase envelop showing the hydrate curve.
- Step 9:** Enter pipeline and insulation thermal properties using base data from table 3.6.
- Step 10:** Re-run model and analysis results for each case.

CHAPTER FOUR

MODEL DESIGN AND SIMULATION

4.1 Arctic Seabed Topography Modelling

The seabed topography for the Omen Lange gas field was modelled using the water depth and pipeline inclination data presented in Table 3.5. After inputting these parameters in the detailed view section of the pipeline design window in PIPESIM, the schematic of the seabed was plotted (Fig. 5.1).

4.2 Pipeline Sizing Criteria and Design

In order to select a suitable pipeline size for the model design, the obtained data from the literature presented in Table 3.1 and Table 3.5 were used in PIPESIM system analysis following step 1 to step 7 of the model design procedure in section 3.3. The suitable and optimal pipeline size was chosen based on the pipeline sizing criteria below:

- Maximum hydraulic capacity and output pressure criteria: The optimum pipeline size was regarded as the minimum pipeline size that will comfortably deliver the maximum hydraulic capacity of 70 MMsm³d⁻¹ from the subsea wellhead to the onshore facility 1st stage separator at a pressure not lower than 9 MPa.
- Erosion criteria: The erosional velocity ratio maximum must be less than or equal to unity when modelled using the API 14e erosion model (solids-free model).
- Corrosion criteria: The maximum gas velocity must not be above the ratio of the empirical constant 183 and the square-root of the mixture density in order to reduce the rate of internal pipeline corrosion. Velocity was determined as 14ms⁻¹ using equation 4.1 below.

$$V_e = \frac{C}{\sqrt{\rho_{mixture}}} \quad (4.1)$$

Where, V_e is the erosional velocity, C is a constant = 183, and $\rho_{mixture}$ is the mixture density.

4.3 Hydrate Formation Temperature (HFT) Determination

The compositional PVT model in PIPESIM framework and multiflash PVT package was used to determine the hydrate formation temperature by inputting the well-stream composition presented in Table 3.2 and Table 3.3 in accordance to step 1 to 5, and step 8 of the model design procedure defined in section 3.3. The hydrate temperature was determined in PIPESIM based on Towler and Mokhatab (2005) correlation stated as equation 4.2 below.

$$T_h = 13.47 \ln(P) + 34.27 \ln(SG) - 1.675 [\ln(P) \times \ln(SG)] \quad (4.2)$$

Where, T_h is the gas temperature (°F), P is the flowing pressure (psig), SG is the specific gravity.

4.4 Pipeline Heat Transfer Analysis

The amount of heat transferred out of the pipeline between the fluid inlet at the wellhead and the discharge point was important in order to ascertain how much thermal insulation or inhibition was required to ensure the fluid temperature does not fall below the determined hydrate formation temperature at any location along the pipeline.

The minimum fluid flowing temperature at various distance along the 120 km pipeline was determined using the data presented in Table 3.5 and Table 3.6 by following steps 6 and 9 of the model design procedure in section 3.3. Equation 4.3 is the governing equation used in PIPESIM to model the heat transfer per unit length of pipe.

$$Q = UA(T_b - T_a) \quad (4.3)$$

Where Q is the heat transfer per unit area, U is the overall heat transfer coefficient, A is the radial pipe area, T_b is the bulk fluid temperature and T_a is the ambient temperature.

4.5 Design of Case I: Thermal Insulation

In the event that the minimum flowing temperature of the fluid is below the hydrate temperature determined, thermal insulation was one of the alternatives used as a method to conserve the heat by reducing the overall heat transfer of the fluid to the surrounding. The thermal insulation philosophy for the Ormen Lange 120 km pipeline was a wet insulation with Polypropylene (PP) material of $0.21 \text{ W (m.C)}^{-1}$ thermal conductivity.

The extent of thermal insulation required was determined following similar approach and data used in section 4.4 above. However, to obtain the overall heat transfer coefficient (OHTC) that met the high-temperature requirement, the insulation material thickness was varied until the expected OHTC at which the maximum turndown and peak production rates were delivered through the pipeline above the design hydrate formation temperature.

The OHTC was modelled in PIPESIM based on equation 4.4 below.

$$\frac{1}{UA} = R_T = R_i + R_p + \sum R_c + R_e \quad (4.4)$$

Where R_T is the total resistance, R_i , R_e are the internal and external film resistance to convective heat transfer, R_p is the resistance to heat conduction through the pipe, and R_c is the resistance to heat conduction through the insulation material which are influenced by the pipe and insulation material thermal conductivity.

A safety margin of 5°C was added to the Multiflash hydrate temperature obtained from the model of section 4.3 for this design to make allowance due to the high risk of hydrate and ice formation in the Arctic field.

The design was in three layers of fusion bonded epoxy (FBE) for corrosion prevention, an adhesive which enables chemical bonding between the FBE and the multiple layers of polypropylene heat insulation system. Wet solid polypropylene insulation was used because it offered a multilayer configuration which provides flexibility in the design pattern, good resistance to temperature loss, buoyancy for the pipeline, and has no water depth limitation within the range of the case study field.

4.6 Design of Case II: Mono-Ethylene Glycol Injection

In order to tell the amount of MEG that will effectively suppress the hydrate temperature and ensure the produced fluid flows outside the hydrate formation temperature, the weight percent of MEG (wt% MEG) and the rate at which it will be injected was computed. The MEG concentration required to inhibit hydrate formation in the pipeline is taken as the sum of the amount required in the:

- Aqueous Phase
- Vapour Phase
- Hydrocarbon Liquid Phase

Although the amount of the inhibitor in the vapour and liquid hydrocarbon phase contributes nearly nothing to the inhibition, accounting for it improves the design accuracy. But for this design, only losses to vapour phase was accounted for since no liquid hydrocarbon was in the produced fluid composition used for the study.

After computing the wt%MEG, the obtained value was inputted into Multiflash software to ascertain the impact of this amount of MEG injection on the hydrate formation temperature which was shown on the hydrate curve shown in Fig 5.9.

The Following steps were taken to determine all the results needed for the MEG injection:

Step 1: Determine the design hydrate formation and depression point temperature.

The design hydrate formation temperature was obtained from equation 4.5 below.

$$T_{dh} = T_{bh} + T_{sm} \quad (4.5)$$

Where T_{dh} is the design hydrate temperature; T_{bh} is the base hydrate temperature obtained from the model of section 4.3 at maximum pipeline inlet pressure and T_{sm} is the safety margin temperature (5°C).

The hydrate depression point was determined from equation 4.6 below.

$$\Delta T = T_{dh} + T_{min} \quad (4.6)$$

Where ΔT is the hydrate depression point temperature, T_{min} is the minimum pipeline outlet temperature which was obtained from the model result of section 4.3.

Step 2: Determine the wt% of MEG required in the free-water phase.

The validity of Hammerschmidt equation was found to be limited to only 30wt % for MEG. Based on that, the weight percent of MEG in the water phase was computed using the Nielsen and Bucklin (1983) equation (equation 2.3, and 2.4) which is valid up to 80wt% MEG [27].

Step 3: Determine the total amount of water condensed in the system

The data available for this study did not include the detailed water analysis, hence the total amount of water condensed in the pipeline was determined by reading out the fluid pressure and temperature at inlet and outlet of the pipeline from the GPSA chart for water content in lean gas shown in Fig.A.III.1

Based on the results obtained from reading the chart, and the estimated maximum formation water given in Table 3.4, the total amount of water in the pipeline was determined which was a combination of the water condensed and that produced from the formation.

Step 4: Determine the mass of MEG required in the free-water phase per day

The mass of MEG required in the water per day to inhibit the impact of the maximum daily water production rate in the pipeline was determined using equation 4.7.

$$m_{MEG} = T_w \times \left(\frac{X_{MEG}}{100 - X_{MEG}} \right) \quad (4.7)$$

Where m_{MEG} is the mass of MEG, T_w is the total amount of water in the system, X_{MEG} is the wt% MEG

Step 5: Determine the amount of MEG loss to the vapour phase.

The maximum possible MEG loss to vapour was determined from the literature to be approximately 0.3 kg MEG $(10^6 \text{sm}^3)^{-1}$ gas [14]. In order to avoid the damaging effect of under-design, the maximum possible MEG loss was used for the computation of the MEG losses to vapour by applying equation 4.8 below.

$$V_{MEG} = M_L \times M_{gr} \times X_{MEG} \quad (4.8)$$

Where V_{MEG} is the amount of MEG lost to vapour, M_L is the maximum vapour loss and M_{gr} is the maximum gas rate.

Step 6: Sum the total MEG injection rate required to inhibit hydrate formation.

The total MEG required to inhibit hydrate formation in the pipeline was therefore obtained by taking a sum of the amount required in the water phase and the amount lost to the vapour phase on a daily basis.

4.7 Design of Case II: Methanol Injection

Just like the MEG design completed in section 4.6 above, the concentration of methanol (MeOH) that will suppress adequately the hydrate formation temperature was required in order to ensure the right dose was injected and at the right rate.

The hydrate and depression point temperature evaluated with equation 4.5 and 4.6 remains valid here hence was not re-evaluated.

Step 1: Determine the weight percent of methanol required in the free-water phase.

The weight percent of methanol needed in the water phase was computed using the Hammerschmidt equation (equation 2.2), and K – constant of 1297, M = 32gmol⁻¹.

Step 2: Determine the total amount of water in the system.

The total amount of water obtained in step 3 of MEG design was also valid here.

Step 3: Determine the mass of methanol required in the water phase.

The mass of methanol required in the water phase per day was determined using the equation 4.9 below.

$$m_{MeOH} = T_w \times \left(\frac{X_{MeOH}}{100 - X_{MeOH}} \right) \quad (4.9)$$

Where m_{MeOH} is the mass of methanol, T_w is the total water in the system, X_{MeOH} is the wt% MeOH

Step 4: Calculate the amount of methanol loss to the vapour phase.

Methanol, because of its low molecular mass, some amount tends to go to the vapour phase when injected as such are not utilized for the hydrate inhibition. However because the amount required to inhibit hydrate formation is a combination of the amount required in the water phase and the vapour losses, the design accounted for the vapour losses.

For the purpose of this study, the amount of MeOH lost to the vapour was determined using the Vapour-liquid equilibrium chart shown in Fig.A.III.2 at the output temperature and pressure obtained from the model design of section 4.4. The total MeOH lost to vapour was computed using equation 4.9.

Step 5: Sum the total methanol injection rate required to inhibit hydrate formation.

Total daily Methanol injection rate required was determined by taking a sum of the amount required in the liquid phase and the total MeOH lost to vapour:

4.8 Design of Case III: Direct Electric Heating (DEH)

The direct electric heating system was designed to provide electric power to the pipeline as an active heat source to keep the pipeline heated above the hydrate formation temperature at all operating condition of the pipeline.

However, in order to consider direct electrical heating for the 0.762m (30") Ormen Lange subsea to shore pipeline, the design was performed as a prototype of the SINTEF DEH technique, by supplying the electric power for the pipeline heating to numerous sections of the pipeline as shown in Fig. 4.1. This way, the distance between each heat injection point was reduced and the heating efficiency improved [24].

The open loop system of DEH was the method used in this design, the basic theory involved connecting two alternating currents (AC) carrying cables to both ends of the pipe to be heated so as to create a closed-circuit as shown in Fig. 4.1. Overtime, as the current was continuously supplied through the cable to the metal conductor, an ohm force was generated which caused an energy loss and consequently produced heat on the pipeline wall from which the bulk fluid was heated.

The heating power was assumed to be supplied from the onshore processing facility which therefore required power cable/umbilical, high voltage penetrators, power transformer, a reactor for reactive power compensation and a static variable compensation (SVC) to compensate for voltage variation due to load changes.

Figure 4.1: Two mid-point sectioned DEH of 120 km Ormen Lange pipeline

The following conditions were assumed in order to decide what parameter was used to obtain the electric power needed to keep the fluid in the pipeline heated above the hydrate formation temperature all-through the pipeline length:

1. The pipeline was partially insulated with a thermal insulation thickness of 0.04m (40mm) and OHTC of $5.44\text{Wm}^{-2}\text{K}^{-1}$ obtained from the model result of section 4.5 and tabulated in Table A.II.1, in order to reduce the rate of heat loss.
2. The piggyback cable (PBC) installation was carried out prior to pipeline insulation to achieve a closer distance with the pipeline approximately 50 mm.
3. The power rating to maintain the flowing fluid outside the design hydrate formation temperature of 26°C was the required powered.

The total electrical power needed to efficiently maintain the operating temperature of the well-stream above the hydrate formation temperature was obtained using equation 4.10 [48] below, which relates the pipeline inlet (wellhead temperature) and the desired operating temperature (design hydrate formation temperature) to the pipe length, fluid heat capacity and the total resistance of the pipe and insulation material.

$$T_1 = \exp \left[\ln(T_2 - R_T \times P_w) - \frac{L}{R_T C_p} \right] + R_T \times P_w \quad (4.10)$$

Where P_w is the power required (W), T_1 and T_2 are the well-stream inlet and the design hydrate formation temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), L is the length of pipeline (m),

C_p is the specific heat capacity of the mixture ($\text{kJ.kg}^{-1}.\text{K}^{-1}$) and R_T is the total resistance of pipe and insulation material to heat loss ($\text{m}^2.\text{K.W}^{-1}$).

Rearranging equation 4.10 in terms of power P_w , the equation becomes:

$$P_w = \frac{T_2 \times \exp\left(\frac{L}{R_T C_p}\right) - T_1}{R_T \times \exp\left(\frac{L}{R_T C_p}\right) - R_T} \quad (4.11)$$

Substituting the following values into equation 4.11 above:

Pipeline inlet temperature T_1 (K)

Design hydrate formation temperature T_2 (K) obtained from section 4.3.

Mixture specific heat capacity C_p ($\text{kJ.kg}^{-1}.\text{K}^{-1}$) obtained from PIPESIM simulation

Pipeline length $L = 120\text{km}$

Total resistance to heat loss R_T obtained at 0.04m thermal insulation thickness.

4.9 Sensitivity Analysis of Variables

The sensitivity analysis of some variables was performed so as to obtain an optimum design condition for this model. The variables sensitized in each of the design case are presented below:

Case I: Thermal Insulation

- The effect of thermal insulation thickness on the fluid flowing temperature in pipeline and OHTC.

Case II: Thermodynamic Chemical Inhibitor

- The weight percent of MEG and Methanol injected.
- The Impact of increasing the water production rate towards the end of field life on output pressure and the amount of chemical required

Case III: Direct Electrical Heating (DEH)

- The effect of increasing the design hydrate temperature on the total amount of electric power required to maintain operation outside hydrate region.

4.10 Economic Evaluation of Thermal Insulation.

Cost was another key factor that influenced the decision of which alternative could be implemented for the Ormen Lange hydrate and low-temperature management, as such, the economic evaluation of each option was also assessed.

The cost implication of developing the Ormen Lange gas field with the selected pipeline size from section 4.2, to obtain the minimum flowing temperature above the design hydrate formation temperature was determined using an estimated polypropylene thermal insulation material cost of \$270 per meter thickness. The detailed analysis of the costing is presented in Table A.I.3.

4.11 Economic Evaluation of Thermodynamic Inhibitor (MEG and MeOH)

The daily volumetric rate of MEG and MeOH obtained from section 4.6 and 4.7 was used to determine the possible OPEX associated with running the gas field with MEG and/or MeOH based on an estimated price of \$2.83 per litre at 99.8 % purity for MEG and \$0.714 per litre at 90% purity for MeOH respectively. The detailed steps taken for the cost estimation is presented in Table A.I.1 and Table A.I.2 respectively.

4.12 Economic Evaluation of DEH

The power required to directly heat-up the pipeline obtained from section 4.5, and the maximum cost of energy published by the Statistisk Sentralbyra Statistics Norway which was approximately 0.35 NOK per kWh, an equivalent of \$0.042 per kWh [49] was used to determine the daily and yearly cost of continuously heating the pipeline above the hydrate formation temperature through a direct electric heating system. The summary of the steps taken for the estimation is presented in Table A.I.4 and Table A.I.5.

CHAPTER FIVE

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 Arctic Seabed Design Results

The Ormen Lange Arctic field seabed model in Fig 5.1 showed a high degree of roughness which presents a high risk of free span that could lead to pipeline fatigue. From the seabed design, between an elevation of -900 m and -200 m, the model showed a continuous upward rise till a distance of 40 km. The implication of this upward rise of the terrain within this distance is that the pressure drop in the pipe when the fluid is flown from the seabed up to the surface along this section of the pipeline will be high.

Also, between a distance of 100 km and 118 km, the seabed showed a high degree of undulation which could cause pipeline misalignment. Therefore in order to avoid the compromise of the pipeline integrity which could lead to rupture and installation failure, prior to the pipe lay, the free span must be determined and possible solutions such as levelling, rock beds, pre-trenching or support structures must be provided.

Figure 5.1: Ormen Lange Terrain Profile

5.2 Pipeline Sizing Results

The results of the system analysis model for the suitable and optimum pipeline size showed that pipeline size 0.635 m (25") could only deliver a maximum hydraulic capacity of 40 MMsm³.d⁻¹ which is nearly half the expected peak production, as such, it is considered not suitable for the tieback design.

However, the model plot in Fig. 5.2 shows that pipeline sizes 0.762 m (30"), 0.914 m (36") and 1.016 m (40") were able to deliver a maximum hydraulic capacity greater than, or equal to the maximum required peak production rate at output pressure above 9 MPa. The erosional velocity was less than unity, and the maximum gas velocity less than 14 ms⁻¹ as shown in the model plot in Fig. 5.3 and Fig 5.4.

Pipeline sizes 0.914 m and 1.016 m gave a lower pressure drop in pipe (higher output pressure) because of their bigger sizes, nevertheless, from a cost and weight standpoint, the bigger the diameter of pipe, the more the cost, and the heavier the weight which is a challenging factor during pipe-lay after adding the thermal insulation thickness. Pipeline size 0.762m (30") was considered the suitable and optimum size for the design with maximum inlet and output pressures of 22 MPa and 12.9 MPa respectively.

Figure 5.2: Maximum Production rate and output Pressure for different pipeline size

The maximum gas velocity is expected to be lower than the erosional velocity because carbon steel specified for the pipeline is a non-corrosion resistant metal, hence high gas velocity will increase the rate of pipe wall sweep, erosion and increase in corrosion rate, particularly considering the fact that 0.30 mole% of CO₂ was in the fluid composition. Also because of the presence of produced water in the system, high-velocity gas will cause liquid slugs which wash away the film protective layers formed by the injected corrosion inhibiting chemicals which will expose the pipeline to a high risk of corrosion.

Figure 5.3: Erosional Velocity Ratio maximum for selected pipeline sizes

Figure 5.4: Maximum gas velocity for selected pipeline size at various flowrates Rate.

5.3 Result of Hydrate Temperature Prediction

The Multiflash phase envelop of Fig.5.5 shows that at maximum pipeline inlet pressure of 220 bara (22 MPa), the hydrate formation temperature is approximately 21°C which is denoted with the yellow dot in the plot. The hydrate temperature of 21°C means that transporting the reservoir fluid below this temperature at pipeline pressure of 220 bara (22 MPa) or above, will result to the formation of gas hydrates in the pipeline.

Similarly, in Fig. 5.5, the ice line indicates the pressure and temperature of the system at which ice will start to form. The result of this model was validated by the work of Sloan [10] on the fact that, even though gas hydrates share some physical properties with ice, hydrates can form at a temperature well above the freezing point.

The aqueous line shows the hydrate free region, although at this region free water and gas exist, because of the high temperature of the gas in this region, the possibility of hydrate formation is not there. This validates the facts that regardless of the amount of water and

gas in the system if the temperature is high enough above the hydrate formation temperature, hydrate will not form.

The hydrocarbon curve shows the hydrocarbon two-phase region enclosed by bubble point and dew point curve which meets at the critical point (a point of similar physical and chemical properties).

The hydrate 1 and hydrate 2 are both hydrate formation line and represent the point of initial hydrate formation (hydrate 2) and the point at which blockage will start to form in the pipeline (hydrate 1) if no remedial action is taken.

All the parts to the right side of the hydrate2 line is considered as hydrate free region, whereas the left side is regarded as the hydrate stability region. But the hydrate stability region could be adjusted by the injection of chemical inhibitors or salts such as NaCl.

Figure 5.5: Multiflash phase envelop showing the hydrate formation temperature

5.4 Pipeline Heat Transfer Analysis Results

The minimum possible temperature of the pipeline serves as a guide to determine the amount of heat required or thermal insulation thickness needed to conserve the well-stream temperature and provide a longer cool-down period in the event of planned or unplanned system shutdown. The result of the model in Fig. 5.6 shows a rapid drop in well-stream temperature from the inlet of 70°C to the ambient sea temperature of -2°C within the first 5km.

However, after a distance of 20km, the temperature started to rise as the ambient sea temperature profile rises along the pipeline and outputs at a temperature of 10.5°C. The swift fall in temperature was due to the convective heat transfer from the hot fluid to the ice-chilled ambient sea and was critical because the pipeline was uninsulated (Bare pipe). The implication of this result is that the possibility of hydrate and ice formation and blockage of flow in the pipeline is very high unless a reasonable amount of inhibition or thermal insulation is applied. The temperature profile of the model in Fig 5.6 was also validated by the findings in the literature that the coolest temperature of the pipeline must be greater or equal to the ambient temperature.

Figure 5.6: Well fluid temperature profile for uninsulated pipeline

5.5 Thermal Insulation Design and Economic Evaluation Results

The model results in Fig. 5.7 indicates that the minimum insulation thickness that could maintain the pipeline fluid temperature above the design hydrate temperature of 26°C for both maximum turndown and ramp-up operations is 180 mm (0.18m) and the OHTC at this insulation level was obtained as 1.40 W.m⁻².K⁻¹.

In other words, the result implies that the highest acceptable rate of heat transfer from the pipeline to the ambient sea must be less or equal to 1.40 W.m⁻².K⁻¹ in order to maintain the fluid temperature above the design hydrate formation temperature using polypropylene thermal insulation material.

The analysis also showed a relationship between the thickness of the thermal insulation material applied and the amount of heat conserved in the pipeline which is reflected on the value of the OHTC and the output temperature at various insulation thickness as shown in the sensitivity analysis of Fig 5.8. As the insulation thickness increases from zero to 0.2m, the OHTC reduces at the same trend from 40 W.m⁻².K⁻¹ to a lower value of 0.14 W.m⁻².K⁻¹ whereas the output temperature increased from 5.1°C to 27°C and yet showed the tendency of a further increase as long as the thermal insulation thickness increased.

Similarly, the low one-off investment cost presented in Table 5.3 required for the implementation of complete thermal insulation, in addition to its environmental friendliness due to the fact that it is well-known and practiced technology compared to other thermal alternatives makes it a considerable option. And from the model plot in Fig 5.8, it is shown to be a possible alternative under steady state operating condition as it was able to keep the fluid temperature outside the hydrate formation region all-through the length of the pipeline at the design insulation thickness and thermal properties.

However, although thermal insulation maybe technically feasible, the reliability of this method to continuously prevent the formation of hydrate at all operating conditions was not guaranteed, particularly for gas dominant system. This is because gases have low thermal mass which increases the rate of heat loss as well as reduces the cooldown or no-touch period once the active heating source is removed or shutdown. The inability of the thermal insulation to maintain the pipeline heat during transient conditions such as long

shutdown, shut-in and restart- up are major setbacks of the method when considering it for long distance tiebacks and low temperature operating environment such as the Arctic.

Figure 5.7: Well fluid temperature profile at 180mm Insulation thickness

Figure 5.8: Sensitivity analysis of insulation thickness effect on fluid output temperature and OHTC

Table 5.3: Thermal Insulation Requirement and Cost

Parameter Description	Unit Value	Unit Quantity	Sum Cost (million \$)
Cost of Pipeline (\$/km)	755	120	0.0906
Insulated Pipeline installation (\$/km)	1,000,000	120	120
Insulation Material Cost (\$/m)	270	21600	5.832
Total CAPEX			126

5.6 Results from MEG Injection Design and Economic Evaluation

The design results for the weight percent and optimum injection rate of MEG required to suppress the hydrate formation temperature of the system in order to assure the flow of the produced fluid outside the hydrate formation temperature are summarised in Table 5.4.

The injection of the estimated 45.3 wt% of MEG at an injection rate of 216.232 m³day⁻¹ showed a great suppression of the hydrate formation curve from an initial uninhibited hydrate formation temperature of 21 °C to a lower temperature of 2 °C at the same inlet pressure of 22 MPa as shown in the Multiflash phase envelop of Fig. 5.9.

The result of the MEG design simply means that a continuous injection of MEG at the determined rate and weight percent, will assure the flow of the produced fluid in the pipeline at 22 MPa pressure and temperature as low as 2 °C without hydrate formation in the pipeline. Also, in the event of a long shutdown, increasing the weight percent of MEG injected to obtain a suppression temperature that is lower or equivalent to the minimum ambient temperature will keep the fluid outside the hydrate formation.

The model result was also validated from the findings in the literature review that three basic factors influence the amount of MEG required to inhibit the hydrate formation in any Arctic pipeline which are:

1. The total amount of free-water in the pipeline (condensed plus formed)
2. The wellhead flowing temperature and pressure of the wellstream (pipeline inlet temperature and pressure).
3. The output temperature and pressure of the wellstream (pipeline output temperature and pressure).

The validity of the above three conditions is in agreement with McKetta and Wehe results on water content of natural gas [50]. When the wellhead (inlet) pressure of the gas starts to decrease at a constant temperature, the amount of water condensed will increase, at the inlet. Similarly, when the inlet temperature is increased at constant pressure, the water condensed at the inlet will also increase, and the outlet condition follows similar behaviour.

This increase in the amount of condensed water due to a decrease in the pipeline inlet pressure will automatically affect the total amount of water in the system, which in-turn influences the mass of the inhibitor (MEG) required in the liquid phase as shown in the sensitivity analysis of Fig 5.10.

The implication of the sensitivity analysis in Fig 5.10 is that towards the end of the field economic life when the reservoir pressure have been depleted which also reduces the wellhead pressure the amount of chemical inhibitor needed to inhibit hydrate formation will be increased because of high water condensation. Similarly, during this period, the amount of formation water produced also increases because the hydrocarbon is greatly depleted and the aquifer is risen, which also means an increase in the amount of MEG required to inhibit the formation of hydrate. This potential increase in the amount of hydrate required towards the end of field life is a setback for the MEG chemical injection.

Also, the economic evaluation for MEG shown in Table 5.5 revealed that the capital cost of the investment is higher compared to other alternatives, which was obviously because of the glycol regeneration unit installation, but the advantage of such investment was also seen in the operational cost.

Table 5.4: Summary results for MEG injection design, OPEX and CAPEX.

Parameters	Values and units
Design hydrate formation temperature	26°C
Weight percent of MEG required in water phase	45.3wt% MEG
Total free water in pipeline (formation + Condensed)	240,148 kgday ⁻¹
Mass of MEG required in water phase	198,879kg.day ⁻¹
MEG Vaporization Losses	951 kg.day ⁻¹
Total Amount of MEG required to suppress hydrate formation in the multiphase pipeline	241,099 kg.day ⁻¹ (216,232litre.day ⁻¹)

Table 5.5: Summarised results for MEG injection design, OPEX and CAPEX.

Parameter Description	Cost	
	\$/day	million \$/year
Initial Cost of MEG Injection	611,937	223.4
Additional MEG injection cost	183,580	67
Cost of Heat for regeneration Unit	5000	1.8
OPEX for MEG injection	800,517	292.2
CAPEX for MEG injection		\$ 878.5

Figure 5.9: Impact of MEG injection on Hydrate formation curve

Figure 5.10: MEG mass required in water phase at various inlet pressure

5.7 Results from Methanol Injection Design and Economic Evaluation

The design results for methanol injection rate and weight percent needed to suppress the hydrate formation temperature of the wellstream to assure free flow of the produced fluid is summarised in Table 5.6. The impact of injecting the estimated 27.7 wt% of MeOH at an injection rate of $160.44 \text{ m}^3\text{day}^{-1}$ in suppressing the hydrate formation temperature from an initially determined 21°C (when no chemical is injected) to a lower temperature of 8°C is shown in the hydrate curve of the Multiflash model for methanol injection in Fig. 5.11.

The result therefore means that injecting a continuous 27.7 wt% of MeOH will constantly prevent the fluid temperature from falling into the hydrate region as the hydrate temperature is suppressed by the Methanol. Similarly, increasing the concentration of the methanol injected will shift further the hydrate curve towards the left thereby increasing the hydrate free zone, which implies that the level of suppression obtainable is dependent on the amount of chemical injected.

Table 5.6: Summary Results for Methanol Injection Design

Parameter Description	Values and units
Design hydrate formation temperature	26°C
Weight percent of MeOH required in water phase	27.7 wt%
Total free water in pipeline (formation + Condensed)	$240,148 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$
Mass of MeOH required in water phase	$92,007 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$
MeOH Vaporization Losses	$34,902 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$
Total Amount of MeOH required to suppress hydrate formation in the multiphase pipeline	$126,909 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$ ($160,440 \text{ litre}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$)

Figure 5.11: Impact of Methanol injection on the Hydrate formation curve

However, in addition to the effect of water volume on the amount of chemicals injected, the methanol injection design also identified two major factors that influence the amount of methanol concentration required for a particular gas stream, which are:

1. The Output temperature and pressure
2. The total amount of methanol vaporization losses

The validity of the above factors was supported by the GPSA analysis of methanol-water vapour-liquid equilibrium [6]. The design identified that an increase in the output pressure at constant output temperature, caused a reduction in the amount of methanol lost to the vapour, whereas reducing the pressure at the same temperature increases the vaporization losses.

The implication of this will be that, for methanol injection, as the reservoir pressure declines due to continuous depletion, if the gas does not get any form of pressure boosting to maintain the high pressure, the vaporization losses of the injected methanol will increase, when this undesirable high losses is added to the required higher methanol volume due to the predicted increase in water production rate towards the end of field life, the overall required methanol at this period will be too high to be an economical best option.

From a cost perspective, the economic evaluation of methanol in Table 5.7 shows it has a low investment cost. However because of the high vaporization losses shown in Table 5.6, the OPEX when methanol is used as a hydrate management strategy still runs very high, and the damaging effect of the continuous bullheading of methanol in the produced reservoir fluid has become both a refinery challenge, environmental threat and produced fluid specification concern.

Table 5.7: Summary of the OPEX and CAPEX for Methanol Injection

Parameter Description	Cost	
	USD/day	USD/year
OPEX for MeOH injection	1,232,049.74	449,698,155.10
CAPEX	328,500,000 USD	

5.8 Results from DEH Design and Economic Evaluation

The result of the DEH assessment in Table 5.8 shows that the power rating required to keep the pipeline heated above the design hydrate formation temperature of 26 °C was 1,627 kW.km⁻¹ and a total power consumption for the entire length of the pipeline was 195.24 MW.

The implication of this result is that heating the pipeline electrically in sections with this power rating will maintain the temperature of the bulk fluid outside the hydrate temperature as long as the power is supplied.

Also, from Table 5.8, the cost-impact of DEH was found from the assessment to be reasonably low, which makes it an attractive option for hydrate management particularly for transients' conditions such as shut-in, long period planned and unplanned shutdown and plug removal.

Figure A.II.1 shows a direct relationship between the power required and the design hydrate formation temperature, as such, depending on the thermal properties of the pipeline and insulation material, a desired hydrate dissociation temperature is achievable when the required power is available.

Table 5.8: Results from DEH Design and Economic Evaluation

Parameters Description		Values
Power Required per km		1,627kW.km ⁻¹
Total Power Required for 120km		195.24MW
Cost of energy per kWh		\$ 0.042 (kWh) ⁻¹
Capital investment (CAPEX)		\$ 318,902,001
OPEX	Daily	\$ 196,802 day⁻¹
	Yearly	\$71, 832,701 year⁻¹

CHAPTER SIX

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

6.1 Conclusion

In this study, it was found that thermal insulation method of pipeline heat conservation has the lowest overall investment cost and requires little or no routine maintenance operation which further reduce its cost impact and amount of pollution traced to it. However the study also revealed that it lacked reliability and good performance when considering gas pipeline insulation and transient conditions particularly for long step-out tiebacks such as the Ormen Lange.

Similarly, the direct electric heating method was found relatively to be a less hazardous alternative, but on the condition that the quality assurance and reliability of the piggyback power cable and its insulation is not compromised, because if otherwise, the risk of stray current and/or emission from the station could be triggered. It was also discovered that the DEH have low CAPEX and OPEX when compared to the thermodynamic chemicals, yet was capable of heating the pipeline at all operating conditions.

On the other hand, methanol was found to be a high OPEX alternative. Findings from the assessment revealed that the vaporization losses was too high which made both its low weight percent required to suppress hydrate temperature in the water phase and the market value per volume not felt on the overall when compared to the counterpart MEG in addition to its toxicity.

MEG from the assessment was found to have nearly a negligible amount of vapour losses, and less harmful nor toxic with good suppression of hydrate temperature in the water phase. Nevertheless, the investment cost was way above that of other alternatives considered.

Summarily, findings from this research has shown that thermal insulation, direct electric heating (DEH) and thermodynamic chemical injection alternatives considered were found feasible, however with unique limitations and highpoints, but with respect to cost, reliability and environmental impacts the DEH was considered the optimum alternative in this assessment.

6.2 Recommendations

Following the findings from this research, I hereby recommend that:

- ✓ Further studies and possibly a detailed modelling of the DEH method by section should be carried out to validate the possibility and reliability of such system for long distance tiebacks above 100km and harsh conditions like the Arctic.
- ✓ A lab analysis should be performed to investigate the implication of mixing MEG and methanol prior to injection as a way of giving MeOH some viscosity to reduce vaporization loss and also reduce the amount of MEG injected to save cost on the overall.

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Appendix I

Economic Analysis of Design Cases.

The cost of the equipment and materials used for this analysis were averages of the amount found in three commercial vendors assessed during this research which include: Alibaba, ebay and Amazone. The Installation cost were all assumed based on findings from other feasibility studies in the open literature. The purpose of this estimates was just to demonstrate understanding and give an overview of what is required in terms of CAPEX and OPEX for hydrate management strategy in the Arctic region.

Table A.I.1: Summarised Cost Analysis for MEG

Parameters Descriptions	Unit Cost	Unit Quantity	Sum Cost (USD)
Coated Pipeline Installation cost (\$/km)	1,000,000	120	120,000,000
Pipeline Cost (\$/km)	755,000	120	90,600,000
MEG Injection Pipelines (\$/km)	500,000	120	60,000,000
subsea Power Umbilical cost (\$/km)	250,000	122	30,500,000
High pressure Circulation pump (\$)	1,700,000	2	3,400,000
Glycol regeneration Unit (\$)	550,000,000	1	550,000,000
Chemical Storage tank	12,000,000	2	24,000,000
MEG Injection Project Execution CAPEX			878,500,000
Injection rate of MEG Injection (litre/day)	2.83	216,232	611,936.56
Added volume Cost (30% Main injected volume) (litre/day)	2.83	64869.6	183,580.97
Cost of Heat for regeneration Unit (\$/day)	5000	1	5,000.00
MEG Operation OPEX (\$/day)			800,517.53
MEG Operation OPEX (\$/year)			292,188,897.72

- ❖ Parameter cost = Unit cost * Unit Quantity
- ❖ Additional volume = 30% Original volume injected to inhibit hydrate formation
- ❖ Cost of MEG injected = Unit cost (\$2.83/litre) * Unit quantity (litre/day)

Table A.I.2: Summarised Cost Analysis for Methanol Injection

Parameters Descriptions	Unit Cost	Unit Quantity	Sum Cost (USD)
Coated Pipeline Installation cost (\$/km)	1,000,000	120	120,000,000
Pipeline Cost (\$/km)	755,000	120	90,600,000
MeOH Injection Pipelines (\$/km)	500,000	120	60,000,000
subsea Power Umbilical cost (\$/km)	250,000	122	30,500,000
High pressure Circulation pump (\$)	1,700,000	2	3,400,000
Chemical Storage tank	12,000,000	2	24,000,000
MeOH Injection Project Execution CAPEX			328,500,000
Injection rate of MeOH Injection (litre/day)	0.71	1,667,634	1,184,020.14
Produced water treatment for MeOH and disposal(\$/Sm ³)	200	240.148	48,030
MeOH Operation OPEX (\$/day)			1,232,049.74
MeOH Operation OPEX (\$/year)			449,698,155.10

Table A.I.3: Summarised Cost Analysis for Thermal Insulation

Parameter Description	Unit Value	Unit Quantity	Sum Cost (USD)
Cost of Pipeline (\$/km)	755	120	90600
Insulated Pipeline installation (\$/km)	1,000,000	120	120000000
Insulation Material Cost (\$/m)	270	21600	5832000
			125,922,600

Table A.I.4: Summarised Cost Analysis for DEH of 120 km Ormen Lange tieback

Parameters Descriptions	Unit Value	Unit Quantity	Sum Cost (USD)
Insulated Pipeline Installation cost (\$/km)	120,000,000	120	120,000,000
Pipeline Cost (\$/km)	90,600,000	120	90,600,000
Insulation material Cost per thickness (\$/m)	1,296,000	4,800	1,296,000
Power Umbilical cost (\$/km)	30,500,000	122	30,500,000
Electric Heating Cable (\$/km)	37,500,000	500	75,000,000
60 MVA Power Transformer cost (\$)	1,000,000	1	1,000,000
HV Penetrators cost (\$)	6,000	1	6,000
Static Variable Compensation cost (\$)	500,000	1	500,000
DEH Execution CAPEX			318,902,000
Power required (kW)	195,240		
Energy cost \$/kWh	0.042		
Cost of Electric Heating (\$/day)	196801.92		
DEH Operation OPEX (\$/year)			71832700.8
DEH Execution an Operation Total Cost (USD)			390,734,701
**insulation material unit quantity = insulation thickness multiplied by total distance(0.04m * 120km)			
**The electric cable unit quantity = 4 * 125 because of the chosen method for power supply.			

Table A.II.1: Pipeline minimum output temperature and OHTC at different insulation thickness.

Polypropylene insulation thickness (mm)	Output temperature (°C)	OHTC (W/m ² /K)
(Uninsulated)	10.5	414.8
40	13.6	5.44
60	18.0	3.72
80	20.8	2.86
100	22.8	2.33
120	24.2	1.98
140	25.3	1.74
160	26.5	1.60
180	27.0	1.40
200	27.5	1.28

Appendix II: Sensitivity Analysis Plots and Tables.

Figure A.II.1: Sensitivity of the change in design hydrate dissociation temperature on the power required in pipeline.

Figure A.II.2: Sensitivity of the effect of increase in MeOH wt%

Figure A.II.3: Sensitivity of the effect of increase in MEG wt%

Appendix III

Water Contents of Hydrocarbon Natural Gas by GPSA

Figure A.III.1: Water Contents of Hydrocarbon Natural Gas: Adapted from [6]

Methanol-Water Vapour-Liquid Equilibrium Chart by GPSA

Figure A.III.2: Prediction of methanol vaporization loss Adapted from [6]

School Of Engineering

Risk Assessment

(Guidance notes to be read prior to completing risk assessment)

Title of project	Flow Assurance Assessment for Arctic Conditions	
Description of work	The Research Involved the modelling of a gas pipeline to transport produced gas from an ice-chilled, and severe Arctic environment but assuring no restriction such as gas hydrates hinders the success of the fluid delivery to the processing platform.	
Principal Investigator(s)	Azubuike, Nyeso Christian	
Supervisor(s)	Dr. David Vega-Maza	
Location of work	Aberdeen of University, King's College Campus	
Start date	Predicted end date	
22 May 2017	14 August 2017	

List of major equipment, materials and facilities involved
Computer screen, and books from library shelves
<p>Step 1 – <u>Identify the hazards.</u></p> <p><i>Spot hazards by:</i> walking around your workplace; considering the equipment you are using; ask your supervisor, technician or fellow students what they think; visit the University safety website; check manufacturers’ instructions or data sheets. Remember to think about long-term hazards to health.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Ergonomic risks of sitting on desk and using a computer for extended periods ii. Impairment to sight due to radiation from computers iii. Fall and trip hazards at Library and computer rooms iv. Stress involved in sourcing information, analysing data and developing a convincing argument
<p>Step 2- <u>Decide who might be harmed and how.</u></p> <p><i>Identify groups of people. Remember:</i> some staff or students have particular requirements; people may not be in the workplace all the time; members of the public; How does your work affect others who share the workplace? Say how the hazard could cause harm.</p>
<p>The Research Work involved the researcher only, as such He was the only person exposed to the risk at a time.</p>
<p>Step 3 – <u>Evaluate the risks and decide on precautions.</u></p> <p><i>What are you already doing?</i> List what is already in place to reduce the likelihood of harm or make any harm less serious.</p> <p><i>What further action is necessary?</i> You need to make sure that you have reduced risks ‘so far as is reasonably practicable’. Compare what you are already doing with good practice and if there is a difference write down what needs to be done.</p>
<p>The library and computer rooms are equipped with adjustable chairs and computers to help in meeting the ergonomic needs of different researchers. The brightness and other settings of the computer screens can also be adjusted to comfortable levels.</p> <p>I would have to schedule my work time to allow for thorough research balanced with physiological requirements to manage stress.</p>

Step 4 – Record your findings and implement them.

Remember to prioritise. Deal with those hazards that are high-risk and have serious consequences first. Decide on actions and by whom.

Ergonomics:	Used adjustable sit and computers
Sight Impairment:	Sit arm stretch distance from screen
Fall and tips trip:	Real time safety consciousness and observe wet floors
Fatigue:	Taking periodic rest from during research

Step 5 - Review Your Assessment and update if necessary.

Make sure that you are still improving and not rolling back. If there is a significant change in your workplace or method, remember to check your risk assessment and where necessary amend it.

Review date: 10 August, 2017

<u>Prepared by</u> Azubuike, Nyeso Christian	<u>Signature</u> 	<u>Date</u> 10-August-2017
<u>Approved by</u>	<u>Signature</u>	<u>Date</u>
Copy in School Office?		
Copy in Laboratory?		

MSc Oil and Gas – Individual Project Guidelines – 2016–17

H Ethical Review Check-list

UNDERGRADUATE AND TAUGHT POSTGRADUATE DISSERTATION ETHICAL REVIEW CHECK-LIST

The University Research Ethics & Governance Framework applies to all aspects of research undertaken within the University, including student dissertations. All PGT students and UG Honours students preparing dissertation proposals should consider the ethical dimensions of their dissertation research using the self-assessment check-list below and, where necessary, seek ethical review and approval.

Ethical review should be sought for any project that answers **YES** to any one or more of the following questions:

	YES/NO
Does the research involve public surveys or questionnaires?	No
Will the subjects of the study include staff or students of the University, or colleagues in a work environment?	No
Does the research involve children or vulnerable adults?	No
Does the research involve any clinical procedure or involve clinical populations?	No
Could the study induce psychological stress or anxiety?	No
Does the research involve human remains?	No
Does the project involve the collection of material that could be considered of a sensitive personal, medical or psychological nature, or constrained by other data protection requirements?	No
Does the project use covert research techniques?	No
Does the research involve the collection, preservation and use of sound and/or video material involving human subjects?	No
Is there any potential for conflict of interest between research funder, investigators and/or participants that may affect funding, dissemination or other research outcomes?	No
Does the research have potential for financial incentives to funders, investigators or participants?	No
Is the research likely to disturb the natural environment?	No
Could the research have any impact on national security of any country?	No

Name: _____ Signature: Date: 14/08/2017

In the event an ethical review is required, please complete the College of Physical Sciences Ethics Review and Application Form (Annex A) with your dissertation supervisor, and attach a brief project summary. Please complete and provide a copy of the appropriate Consent Form and a copy of the statement you will provide to research participants which outlines what they are required to do as part of this study.

Most reviews will be undertaken by circulation to appropriate reviewers within the University, and the outcome of the review should be with the applicant within 2 weeks, although very complex proposals may take longer. The outcome of the review will be communicated to you by the Clerk of the College Ethics Board as soon as practicable.

For further information please contact the Clerk to the College Ethics Board in the first instance, copsethics@abdn.ac.uk.